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IMPROVEMENT OF METHODOLOGY OF ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS OF INCLUDED FINANCIAL STATEMENTS AND INVESTMENTS IN SUBSIDIARY SOCIETIES

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Abstract: This article describes the theoretical and methodological aspects of the preparation of consolidated financial statements in insurance companies in accordance with the requirements of international financial reporting standards, methods of accounting for investments of insurance companies. The methodology of preparation of consolidated financial statements of insurance companies, its calculation and stages of consolidation are described. Considering the characteristics of insurance companies, guidelines have been developed to address the problems of consolidating financial results, assets and liabilities and cash flows, as well as the preparation of financial statements.

Key words: consolidated financial reporting (CFR), control, joint control, participation in shares, significant impact, proportional consolidation, joint activity, elimination of intra-group operations, business merger, segment reporting, separate financial statements, joint stock company, financial instruments, insurance contracts, assets and liabilities, income and expenses, financial statements of the group of companies.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada sug'urta kompaniyalarida xalqaro moliyaviy hisobot standartlariga muvofiq konsolidatsiyalashgan moliyaviy hisobotlarni tayyorlashning nazariy va metodologik jihatlari, sug'urta kompaniyalari investitsiyalarini hisobga olish usullari yoritilgan. Sug'urta kompaniyalarining konsolidatsiyalashgan moliyaviy hisobotlarini tayyorlash metodologiyasi, uning hisoblash tartibi va konsolidatsiyalash bosqichlari izohlangan. Sug'urta kompaniyalari faoliyatining o'ziga xos jihatlari inobatga olgan holda moliyaviy natijalar, aktivlar va majburiyatlar hamda pul oqimlarini konsolidatsiyalashdagi muammolarni hal qilish va moliyaviy hisobotlarni tayyorlash bo'yicha qo'llanmalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: konsolidatsiyalashgan moliyaviy hisobot (KMH), nazorat, qo'shma nazorat, ulushda ishtirok etish, sezilarli ta'sir, proporsional konsolidatsiya, qo'shma faoliyat, guruh ichidagi operatsiyalarni bartaraf etish, biznes birlashmasi, segment hisobotlari, alohida moliyaviy hisobotlar, aksiyadorlik jamiyati, moliyaviy vositalar, sug'urta shartnomalari, aktivlar va majburiyatlar, daromad va xarajatlar, kompaniyalar guruhi moliyaviy hisobotlari.

Аннотация: В данной статье описаны теоретические и методологические аспекты подготовки консолидированной финансовой отчетности в страховых компаниях в соответствии с требованиями международных стандартов финансовой отчетности, методы учета инвестиций страховых компаний. Описана методология подготовки консолидированной финансовой отчетности страховых компаний, порядок её расчета и этапы консолидации. С учётом особенностей деятельности страховых компаний разработаны рекомендации по решению проблем консолидации финансовых результатов, активов и обязательств, а также денежных потоков и подготовке финансовой отчетности.

Ключевые слова: консолидированная финансовая отчетность (КФО), контроль, совместный контроль, участие в долях, значительное влияние, пропорциональная консолидация, совместная деятельность, устранение внутригрупповых операций, объединение бизнеса, сегментная отчетность, отдельная финансовая отчетность, акционерное общество, финансовые инструменты, страховые контракты, активы и обязательства, доходы и расходы, финансовая отчетность группы компаний.

INTRODUCTION

One of the main directions of modernization of the economy of the republic is the proper management. The country has created a legal framework for systematic accounting and strengthening payment discipline, i.e., the Law "On Accounting" and the "National Accounting Standards".

It is known from the experience of other countries that in the effective management of enterprises it is more appropriate to create them in large groups. In this case, two or more companies merge financially and economically under one company or financial groups. In the event of a merger of a group of business entities under the control of the parent, a consolidated financial statement is prepared.

The main purpose of preparing consolidated financial statements is to fully disclose the results of the corporation's operations and financial position. Unfortunately, the current consolidated financial reporting methodology does not fully meet IFRS (International Financial Reporting Standards) requirements.

The main reasons for the formation of consolidated financial statements are:

- Absorption or merging of assets and capital for the purpose of development of the holding business, division of various businesses into legal units and financial benefits from the process of economic consolidation;
- The constant fluctuations of exchange rates of different countries in the context of inflation, the distribution of corporate profits a controversial process;
- Lack of uniform methods and procedures for bookkeeping and reporting in different countries and countries with a federal system of governance.

The above problems arose in the United States in the early twentieth century. For the first time in 1899, companies were formed in New Jersey on the basis of an economic merger in the form of corporations (holdings). Financial groups consisting of a number of dependent business entities. As of March 12, 1903, U.S. steel had a number of foreign subsidiaries with a combined market capitalization of more than 1 billion US dollars, and for the first time in its history compiled a consolidated financial statement as the largest company in the world [8].

The report became legally binding for the first time since the adoption of IAS 3 (International Accounting Standards), Consolidated Financial Statements, in 1970. In 1979, IFRS 3 was amended to IFRS 27, entitled "Consolidated Financial Statements and Accounting for Investments in Subsidiaries", and in 1983, EU Directive No. 7, Consolidated Accounts, was adopted [8].

According to International Accounting Standards, consolidated financial statements deal with the preparation and presentation of consolidated financial statements for a group of enterprises under the management of a parent. Consolidated financial statements are prepared to meet the need for information on the financial position, results of operations and changes in financial position of a group of enterprises. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his book "Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility - should be a daily rule of every leader".

Further improvement of monetary policy through the use of instruments in line with international experience, ensuring the stability of the national currency and prices in the domestic market" also provides for the use of advanced foreign experience and instruments in the management systems of companies.

The Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 states: use" [1] also raises the issue of establishing cooperation with international financial institutions, including the Committee on International Financial Reporting Standards.

IFRS 15, Receipt of Contracts with Buyers, provides for the introduction of a new procedure for the recognition, measurement and reporting of receipts. Therefore, the organization of calculations in accordance with the requirements of this standard, the presentation of transparent information about income and profit in the financial statements, the means that are understandable to international investors, i.e. the most tested and effective methods and techniques, recognition and evaluation criteria, international rules and principles. The introduction of a methodology for providing reliable, consistent and comparable financial information about a company's revenues, profits and distribution and share of profits using it is a matter of urgency for all countries, especially those applying IFRSs for the first time.

In our country, certain results have been achieved in the harmonization of income and profit accounting with IFRS. In particular, in accordance with IFRS 2 "Income from operating activities" and the Regulation "On the structure of costs and the procedure for determining financial results" developed a procedure for income and financial results in accordance with international standards. Procedures for the preparation, international auditing and publication of financial statements on the basis of IFRSs for enterprises with a share and other enterprises on a voluntary basis will be introduced. Ensuring the effective implementation of these tasks requires scientific research to radically improve the methodology of income and profit accounting and reporting on financial results in accordance with the requirements of international standards in accordance with the requirements of foreign investors and other information users. Therefore, it is important to describe income and profit indicators as an element of financial reporting and to identify their components.

The deepening processes of globalization and integration in the countries of the world are leading to the transition to generally accepted international norms and standards and the growing demand for their observance. This also directly applies to accounting and reporting, which is generally accepted as an "international business language". To date, 1 international conceptual framework, 29 International Accounting Standards (IFRSs) and 17 International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) and 33 interpretations of standards have been put into practice. All joint stock companies, multinational corporations and large companies operating in various sectors around the world, together with their subsidiaries and other affiliates, prepare financial statements in accordance with IFRS on a voluntary basis. Therefore, the number of countries recognizing IFRSs is

increasing. Aligning accounting and reporting with the requirements of international standards, on this basis to achieve global harmonization of financial reporting, the effective use of best practices at the national level is the most pressing issue for all countries.

Unification of financial reporting in the context of modern global economic integration, harmonization of national accounting standards with international standards to improve the investment climate in developing countries, methodological issues of convergence and harmonization of financial reporting, improvement of methodology for classification, recognition, evaluation and reporting; special attention is paid to focused scientific research. These studies have resulted in improvements in financial instruments, operating segments, results of joint ventures, fair value measurement, recognition of contracts, and their presentation in financial statements, as well as additional financial reporting. However, the full implementation of these results has not been achieved in all countries, and the application of IFRSs takes into account the specifics of each country.

In our country, a large-scale work has been carried out to harmonize financial reporting with IFRS and strengthen its regulatory framework, and certain results have been achieved. In particular, the transition to international financial reporting standards, their audit and publication based on international auditing standards has been introduced. As a result of the implementation of international standards in our country, "more than 700 joint-stock companies, 5008 enterprises with foreign investment" are moving to the preparation of financial statements based on IFRS 2. However, these achievements do not mean that the problems of financial reporting in the country have been fully resolved.

ANALYSIS OF THE RELEVANT LITERATURE

The National Association of Accountants and Auditors of Uzbekistan, an organized member of the International Federation of Accountants, has won the right to translate and publish International Auditing Standards into the state language. An important step in this direction was the publication of the 3-volume collection "International Standards for Quality Control, Auditing, Review, Other Confidence and Related Services" in Uzbek, published in 2013 with the official permission of the International Federation of Accountants in cooperation with the Ministry of Finance of Uzbekistan [2].

Due to the lack of a national standard for compilation in the audit activities of the Republic, the International Standard for Related Services 4410 (new edition) "Compilation Agreements" came into force on July 1, 2013, or later for reports on compilation agreements.

Commenting on the need for compilation, Bulbulov F., a Tajik scholar and practitioner, said: includes.

Russian practitioner Tatarintseva E.N. considers the compilation of financial information necessary in three cases: first, the provision of additional audit services (related services) to complete the financial statements in the event that they are not prepared for good reasons; second, the preparation of consolidated financial statements; third, the preparation of accounting (financial) reports in accordance with international financial reporting standards or the transformation (adaptation) of the national report to the international [3].

The work of the above-mentioned scholars examines the methodological issues of recognition, measurement, and presentation in the financial statements of long-term assets, inventories, liabilities, income, and expenses. The scientific work prepared by RD Dusmuratov and U.I. Tulaev studied the theoretical, methodological, and practical aspects of financial reporting. I. Ochilov studied the issues of preparation and submission of financial statements in insurance companies. In his article, Marpatov addressed the issue of bringing the financial statements in line with international standards.

Although the research of these authors is of great scientific and practical importance, in these works the issues of harmonization of financial reporting forms with the requirements of international standards, transformation of financial reporting and application of advanced foreign methods of reporting are not sufficiently disclosed. Moreover, there is not enough scientific work devoted to the study of these problems in an interconnected way and as a whole. All this became the basis for conducting research on this topic, as well as defining its goals and objectives.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Methods of logical observation, critical study of the literature, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, comparison, classification based on certain characteristics, SWOT analysis, modeling, system analysis, and economic analysis were used in the processing of the data obtained during the research.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A merger of enterprises is said to be the merger of one separate enterprise into another or the merger of one enterprise into one economic unit as a result of the acquisition of control over the net assets and production

activities of another enterprise. This is mainly due to the efforts of the owners of a company engaged in any activity to establish several small independent enterprises within that company. This results in certain savings on tax payments.

In most cases, business expansion is a necessity. In this situation, transnational companies will expand their activities worldwide. Consolidation of financial statements is required to monitor the expansion of joint ventures and joint activities of enterprises. "... Reports on mergers and consolidations of enterprises: Financial statements on mergers; consolidated financial statements; financial report on participation in joint ventures" [4].

Table 1. Fundamentals of the formation of financial accounting and reporting as a science.

Basics	Description
Purpose	Providing information users with information about the financial condition of the account, its changes in the impact of transactions, the status and movement of funds, as well as income and expenses for decision-making
Accounting entities	Private enterprises, "partnership societies" *, joint-stock companies, large corporations, production cooperatives and unitary state enterprises, banks and credit organizations, budget organizations and non-governmental non-profit organizations
Subject and object	Assets, liabilities, equity, income and expenses and financial and economic events (processes)
Rules and principles	The basic fundamental rule: continuity of activity, continuity and calculation; Fundamental quality description: consistency, fairness and objective presentation
Method (methods and techniques)	A set of methods and techniques used in the recognition, evaluation, processing, grouping and transmission of information
Procedure and cycle	The most effective logical sequence of accounting actions performed in the recognition, identification, measurement, processing, preparation and presentation of financial statements measured in monetary terms
The product of the accounting process	Financial statements are the product of the results of the accounting process. These include statements and comments on financial position, profit and loss and other comprehensive income, cash flows, changes in equity, accounting policies and explanations.

Modernization of financial reporting as an important support of management means the harmonization of the structure and content of financial reporting in the interests of information users, the introduction of the most advanced methods and techniques in the processing and transmission of information and improved reporting forms.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is gradually transitioning to IFRSs in the modernization of financial reporting. Due to the harmonization of curricula with international practices, the subject "Financial Accounting" was renamed "Financial Accounting and Reporting". In this regard, it is important to bring the science of financial accounting and reporting to the world level in our country and to highlight and systematize in a new interpretation the factors that shape it as a science (Table 1).

Theoretical and methodological aspects of the preparation of consolidated financial statements are recognized in IFRS 10 on consolidated financial statements, IFRS 11 on Joint Venture Agreements, IFRS 27 on Separate Financial Statements or IAS. IFRS 28, Investments in Business Entities and Joint Ventures, discloses the requirements for the practical application of consolidated financial statements.

Joint-stock companies operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan, enterprises with other foreign investments prepare financial statements in accordance with the Law on Accounting and IFRS. To have the above capabilities, the company is required to prepare and present financial statements in accordance with IFRS [5].

The first way is to transform the IFRS-based financial statements into IFRS (Figure 1).

The use of the transformation method in the transition to IFRSs does not result in a 100% result and error-free financial reporting. This is because the financial statements under IFRS are shaped by many factors. It is a very difficult process to fully cover them on the first try. Only in the first transformation should large errors be avoided. The experience of transformation is gradually formed, and as a result, the reliability of the financial statements, which is transformed from year to year, increases. Therefore, companies in Uzbekistan need to

start the IFRS financial reporting transformation today to get good results tomorrow. If companies do not feel the need to prepare financial statements based on IFRS today, they will feel the need to do so tomorrow. Therefore, to meet tomorrow's need, the transformation must begin today. A company that thinks we don't have the staff, the opportunity, the resources, and therefore the need is making a big mistake.

Figure 1. Financial reporting transformation stages.

It is advisable to carry out the transformation process in the following sequence:

First, it is necessary to prepare analytical accounting data, if necessary, the initial documents, which reflect the components of financial statements prepared in accordance with national standards, as well as extensions to the balance sheet, profit and loss and other reporting items.

Second, reclassification, revaluation of assets, liabilities, and elements of private capital. The profit and loss statement also reclassifies and evaluates each relevant item in accordance with international standards. Similarly, measures should be developed to bring other reporting items into line with the requirements of individual international standards [8].

Third, it is necessary to make appropriate adjustments to the level of IFRSs, to develop a schedule of additional wiring.

Fourth, compile a report that meets the requirements of IFRSs after appropriate adjustments have been made using accounting entries.

Fifth, the correct use of terms plays an important role in the transition to IFRSs. Terms in the reports based on national standards, naming of indicators, their abbreviations should be transferred to terms that meet international standards. If the indicator is regrouped, its value based on the assessment meets international standards, but its naming is not appropriate, it will be difficult to read, leading to confusion. Therefore, it is necessary to bring the system of terms in line with international standards [5].

In our view, we need to move from the practice of financial accounting and financial reporting process in the world to the practice of transformational working balance sheet. The working balance sheet is an important table (register) that transfers the balances of accounts to the forms of financial statements based on transformational records.

At the stage of preparation of financial statements, the statement of financial position, profit and loss and other comprehensive income, cash flow statement, changes in equity are prepared using the balance sheets and tables. Once the reports have a positive audit opinion, they are approved by top managers and presented to decision makers.

As a result of consolidation, three calculations are made:

- 1) investment deduction, the elimination method is used.
- 2) deduction of economic transactions, write-off of intra-group transactions.
- 3) deduction of financial transactions, deducting mutual debt relationships within the group for example, the parent company lent to a subsidiary, the transaction should be deducted in the consolidated financial statements.

Table 2. Terms set for consolidation in companies [9].

Ownership level of the insurance company	Ownership share	Accounting methods
There is no material influence, so there is no economic control over capital	<20%	The investment account is based on the LCM principle
There is no material influence, no amon control	20% and 50% respectively	The cost of the investment is calculated in the form of dividends received + the profit of the invested company.
Control (marginal domination)	> 50%	The group needs to be consolidated

The task of collecting financial information typically involves the preparation of financial statements (in which case the entity may or may not have a complete financial statement), but may also collect, classify, and compile other financial information. At the time of compiling the financial statements, the auditor or expert accountant does not express an opinion on the legality and fairness of the financial statements, as this type of service does not involve mandatory audit procedures of the financial statements, the auditor is required to report in the compiled financial information.

Based on the research, in order to bring the regulatory framework and regulation of accounting and financial reporting in the country in line with international requirements, develop general principles of accounting and draft national standards, generalize and introduce best practices in accounting, certification and training of accountants. We consider it expedient to establish the Uzbek Institute of Professional Accounting, which is an independent professional organization. The need for the institute was proved in the research work, its goals and objectives were defined.

In our national literature, accounting is described as a form of representation of work and performance¹⁴. In them, the definitions given in the financial statements did not differ in content from the definitions given in the financial statements. In our opinion, the definition of financial reporting is an integral part of its financial accounting, an important tool and procedure in the implementation of its information function and purpose, as well as the integration of all financial statements in the financial statements. , it should be borne in mind that the need for information on the movement of funds is satisfied. Based on the research, we define “financial reporting” as follows: Financial reporting is a tool for achieving the goals, functions and objectives of financial accounting, which changes the financial position of the enterprise for the past period, its financial and economic performance, cash and equity. is a system that incorporates reliable information and is designed to meet the information users’ need for information for decision-making and control.

Table 3. Compilation of part II of the set of international standards of quality control, audit, review, other assurance and related services [10].

Related services	
400-4699	International Standards for Related Services (ISS)
4400	Agreements on the implementation of agreed procedures for financial information (Former ISA 920)
4410	Agreements on the compilation of financial statements
New and revised standards that have not yet entered into force	
3420	Confidence-building arrangements for the submission of a report on the compilation of approximate financial information included in the prospectus
4000-4699	International Standards for Related Services (ISS)
4410	Compilation agreements (in new edition)

The classification is based on the structure of the financial statements, its composition, coverage of specific cases and circumstances, reports on mergers and consolidations, coverage period, type of economic entity and audit, division into main and additional types. The study systematizes the process of presentation of financial statements, the group of information users, their interest in information and the content of the decisions they make. This allows the structure and content of financial reporting to be tailored to the needs of all users.

International Standard on Related Services (IPSS) 4410 "Financial Reporting Compilation Agreements" is required to be considered in the context of "Introduction to International Standards for Quality Control, Auditing, Review, Confidence and Related Services" defining the scope and competence of IFRS [10].

During the preparation of the consolidated balance sheet, certain items of the parent and subsidiaries are combined. Some items may be separated (written off) as transactions between parent and subsidiaries. For example, the debt of one enterprise under the control of the parent company to another, the transactions between them. In the reporting process, such transactions should not be reflected in the overall results of the accounts. Because transactions, debt repayments and receivables lead to an increase in cash within the company.

If the financial statements used in consolidation have been prepared for different reporting dates, the results of current transactions and other events in the period between the reporting period and the date of the parent's financial statements should be adjusted. But in any case, the difference between the reporting dates should not exceed three months. Consolidated financial statements should be prepared using a single accounting policy. If it is not possible to apply a single accounting policy in the preparation of consolidated statements, this should be disclosed in the parts of the report to which the other accounting policy applies [11].

"Income from operating activities," states that "Income from operating activities is income that results in an increase in equity, except for increases in the value of property owners' equity over the period in which the entity operates" described. There is a need to improve this definition.

This is because the definition does not reflect the nature of the increase in economic benefits in terms of the appearance of assets (cash or assets) and (or) the improvement of asset quality and (or) the settlement of liabilities. In addition, the definition is given to income from operating activities, the definition was actually to be given to income because other income not related to ordinary activities also meets the above definition requirements, so the standard does not consider other income as a separate element of financial reporting. In accordance with the conceptual rules of financial reporting, income is an element of financial reporting, which includes basic income and other income. Second, income is divided into income from ordinary activities in accordance with international standards, basic income and income not related to normal activities.

Financial information is reflected in the financial statements, financial information is provided to users in a timely manner. They identify deviations from the actual data in the reports from plans and budgets and analyze their causes. Managers make corrections, make changes to plans and budgets, and make other important decisions about the operation of the business. External information users also express their views on investing. These decisions have an impact on the entity's plans, budgets, performance, and financial and economic operations for membership-based feedback. As a result, activity accelerates and economic efficiency increases.

On the basis of the developed recommendations, it was proposed to include in the normative legal documents the basic principles of quality description, such as consistency, objectivity and objectivity.

In the second chapter of the dissertation, entitled "Improvement of the methodological framework of the statement of financial position", the essence of the statement of financial position, presentation, recognition, assessment of long-term assets, current assets and liabilities and improvement of the methodological basis of the statement of financial position justified.

The work improved the rules for accounting for machinery and equipment, inventories, which are the main elements of financial reporting, as well as the procedure for identifying the initial cost of machinery and equipment, systematization of current assets, inventory cost formation, liability assessment and classification.

The work proposes a methodology for the recognition of short-term liabilities by foreign scholars and IFRS of the Republic of Uzbekistan, their adaptation to best practices, the transition to a new system of liabilities on wages and related processes, as well as dividends.

In order to bring the content of the information reflected in the statement of financial position in line with international standards, we create the following table (Table 4).

Table 4. A series of information that is directly reflected in the statement of financial position.

77.1 Fixed assets (property: land, buildings, machinery and equipment)
77.2. Intangible assets
77.3. Investment real estate
77.4. Financial assets (excluding 77.5, 77.8, 77.9 and 77.11)
77.5. Investments made on the basis of equity participation
77.6. Biological assets
77.7. Inventories
77.8. Trade and other receivables
77.9. Cash and cash equivalents
77.10. Long-term assets and outgoing group assets classified as held for sale
77.11. Current and deferred tax assets
77.12. Trade and other accounts payable
77.13. Reserves (allocations)
77.14. Financial liabilities (except 77.12 and 77.13)
77.15. Tax liabilities (except 77.16)
77.16. Income tax liabilities
77.17. Private capital and reserves

If the financial statements used in consolidation have been prepared for different reporting dates, the results of current transactions and other events in the period between the reporting period and the date of the parent's financial statements should be adjusted. But in any case, the difference between the reporting dates should not exceed three months. Consolidated financial statements should be prepared using a single accounting policy. If it is not possible to apply a single accounting policy in the preparation of consolidated statements, this should be disclosed in the parts of the report to which the other accounting policy applies.

The application of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) is not a binding document, it is of a recommendatory nature. It does not specify the forms of financial reporting that enterprises are required to submit, as in national standards. IFRSs define the main components of financial statements and the minimum information content that should be reflected in them. The application of IFRSs is a matter for the exclusive competence of the company.

The transition to IFRS or the preparation of financial statements based on IFRS creates the following opportunities [12]:

- Increases the transparency of the company's performance.
- Information users have the opportunity to analyze the financial performance of a single company by period and by comparing the performance of several different companies.
- Creditors, shareholders, lending institutions increase confidence in the company and invest in the company's activities with high confidence, the company's access to credit expands.
- Attracting foreign investment and cooperation with foreign investors will increase.
- Access to world markets, access to raw materials, currency, labor exchanges, international capital markets.
- Managers of the company will have the opportunity to obtain reliable, objective, relevant and timely systematized financial information to make management decisions.
- Provides necessary information for budgeting, planning and strategic development assessment of the company.
- Improving the company's management mechanisms, increasing the company's competitiveness, improving product quality and increasing export potential;
- Eliminate elements of corruption, abuse, tax evasion, looting, localization, homelessness, bankruptcy in companies.
- The system of labor incentives will be radically improved, material interest will increase.
- A strong control system will be installed. The spiritual environment is stabilized. Employees' loyalty to their work, company and country are combined.
- Employees can work on themselves and constantly improve their skills. Interest in professionalism and effort will increase.

The use of the transformation method in the transition to IFRS does not result in a 100% result and error-free financial reporting. This is because the financial statements under IFRS are shaped by many factors. It is a very difficult process to fully cover them on the first try. Only in the first transformation should large errors be

avoided. The experience of transformation is gradually formed, and as a result, the reliability of the financial statements, which is transformed from year to year, increases. Therefore, companies in Uzbekistan need to start the transformation of financial statements on the basis of IFRS today in order to get good results tomorrow. If companies do not feel the need to prepare financial statements on the basis of IFRS today, they will feel the need to do so tomorrow. Therefore, to meet tomorrow's need, the transformation must begin today. A company that thinks we don't have the staff, the opportunity, the resources, and therefore the need is making a big mistake.

Based on several information that must be reflected in the financial statements based on IFRS and best practices, a form of reporting on the financial condition for the purposes of transformation for enterprises operating in the country was proposed. In particular, the part of this report on long-term assets will look like this (Table 5).

Table 5. Reflection of information on long-term assets in the statement of financial position (thousand soums).

Name of indicators	Line code	At the beginning of the reporting year	By the end of the reporting year
Long-term tangible assets, total (040 + 050 + 060):	010	8010337	7147472
Property: initial value of land, building, machinery and equipment (by components)	020	13829829	12857480
Accumulated depreciation	030	6627088	6708713
Property: land, building, machinery and equipment book value (020-030)	040	7202741	6148767
Uninstalled equipment	050	123144	100296
Incomplete capital inflows	060	684452	898409
Book value of long-term intangible assets (by components)	070	-	-
Investment real estate	080	-	-
Long-term receivables and deferred expenses	090	441438	441438
Long-term investments (by components)	100	462560	1235825
Deferred tax assets	110	-	-
Biological assets	120	48450	48450
Part I total (010 + 070 + 080 + 090 + 100 + 110 + 120)	130	8962785	8873185
Long-term and outgoing group assets classified as intended for sale	150	-	-

Compilation of the report "Property: land, buildings, machinery and equipment" to fully meet the information needs of users and to obtain information about the components that must be reflected directly in the statement of financial position or in the comments and explanations in accordance with the requirements of the standards purposeful. The proposed report reflects new indicators, such as asset management, error correction and loss from impairment, and provides a methodological procedure for their calculation. This harmonizes the reports and the indicators reflected in them with IFRSs, and the information is tailored to the needs of users.

Line 040 of the statement of cash flows reflects payments for management and operating expenses, item 050 "Payments for management and operating expenses" in line 050 "Payments for overhead production", line 050 "Payments for management and operating expenses" was recommended. In addition, to increase the transparency of the report, it was suggested to include line 211 "deduction of private capital" in the section related to financial activities. In the introductory part of the report "Information on the movement of foreign currency funds" it was recommended to reflect line 303 "Contributions to the authorized capital", line 304 "Sale of shares to foreign shareholders", line 306 "Received financial assistance". In addition, the expenditure part of the reference was based on the need to include line 311 "Exchange of foreign currency for national currency",

line 314 “Transfer of distributed profits or capital outflows to the founders”, line 316 “Transfer of dividends to foreign shareholders”.

The study provided a scientific analysis of the approaches to the components of the cash flow statement. An improved form of cash flow reporting that meets international and national standards and transformation requirements has been proposed. The study developed transformation formulas for direct and indirect cash flow statement based on the statement of financial position and the statement of profit and loss and other comprehensive income (Table 6).

Table 6. Formulas for calculating the main indicators of the statement of cash flows on current operating activities in direct and indirect ways.

Line	Indicators in the report	Computational formulas	Extension of definitions in formulas
010	Proceeds from the sale of goods (goods, works and services) (PMr)	$PMr = YaS + OS1 \text{ or } - OS2 - QS$	YAR - Gross sales
020	On trade activities:	In this case, receivables are calculated together with VAT	QS - Refunds
020	Payments to suppliers for materials (goods, works and services) (PMx)	$PMx = STT + TZ2 \text{ or } - TZ1 + TS1 \text{ or } - TS2$	OS1.2 - (1) decrease, (2) increase in receivables on accounts receivable
040	In terms of production activities:	$PMx = IChM + MZ2 \text{ or } - MZ2 + QQS + QQS2 \text{ or } - QQS1 + TS1 \text{ or } - TS2$	STT - Cost of goods sold
050	Cash paid to suppliers for materials (goods, works and services) (including VAT) (PMx)	In this case, accounts payable on accounts payable, including VAT	TZ1.2 - (1) decrease, (2) increase in inventory balance

Enterprise costs have an inversely proportional effect on financial results. They are mainly funds spent on the purchase of property and labor resources and are a mandatory payment for the enterprise. Another object of accounting for financial results in enterprises is net profit. It is the main source of economic activity of the enterprise and an important indicator of efficiency.

Accounts receivable are monetary assets. Because its extinction is done in the form of money transfer or cash. In national and international accounting standards, accounts receivable is stated at cost. Accounts receivable are set up as a provision for doubtful debts. Accounts receivable of an enterprise that are not repaid on time and are not backed by appropriate guarantees are recognized as doubtful debts. Today, this indebtedness is determined on the basis of an assessment of the borrower's financial condition and the probability of full or partial repayment of the loan amount. This poses some problems in the timely repayment or repayment of this debt.

This means that the normative documents do not provide specific information on the amount of the reserve for this debt and from which source it is formed (including the Tax Code or National Accounting Standards).

In view of the above, we consider it appropriate to define financial instruments as follows: “Financial instruments are financial assets of one party and financial liabilities or other equity instruments of the other party arising from contracts or other documents of a financial nature.” In our view, this definition more fully describes the true nature of financial instruments.

Hence, the financial instruments listed in the International Financial Reporting Standards are the mutual contractual relations of individuals and legal entities, which can be bilateral or multilateral. In it, one party, i.e., the enterprise (organization) or individual, has a financial asset and the other party has a financial liability or equity instruments. The concept of financial instruments is divided into three: financial assets, financial liabilities, and equity instruments [13].

The business entity must have a system for collecting and processing information that allows it to calculate income and expenses during the reporting period to determine the efficiency of its business activities and make management decisions for the next period. In this regard, we believe that the above proposals for the

formation of financial results are of practical importance. Given the fact that the main share in the current assets of tourism enterprises are receivables, proposals were made to re-enter the information “On receivables and payables.” This will be an important support in the analysis of the financial condition of tourism enterprises and effective management decisions. The methodological procedure for calculating the change in equity allows to provide reliable and accurate information in the financial statements. We propose to reflect the components of private capital in the statement of financial position in the following order (Table 7).

The table shows that private capital consists of authorized capital, issue capital, reserve capital, retained earnings, target revenues and reserves for expected expenses and payments. In contrast to the current balance sheet, the authorized capital was divided into share capital and share capital. In joint-stock companies, the procedure for reflecting the share capital of preferred shares and ordinary shares with the nominal value, the number of authorized shares, the number of issued shares was proposed. This serves to increase the transparency of the balance sheet.

Table 7. Reflect the components of private equity in the statement of financial position.

I I. Liabilities and private capital	Line	Computational formulas	Extension of definitions in formulas
	240	5419278	-1065969
Private capital (250 + 280 + 290 + 300 + 310 + 320 + 330)	250	598250	598250
Authorized capital (260 or 270)	260		
Share capital (261 + 262)	270	598250	598250
Share capital (271 + 272-290)	271		
Preference shares — face value X, number of shares allowed X, number of shares issued X	272	598250	598250
The nominal value of ordinary shares is 1000 soums, the number of permitted shares is 598250, the number of issued shares is 598250	280	129127	129127
Emission (added) capital	290		
The number of own shares purchased is X	300	2862277	2851981
Reserve capital	310	1806478	-4668473
Retained earnings	320	23146	23146
Targeted revenues	330		
Reserves for expected expenses and payments	340	5419278	-1065969

In order to reflect the authorized capital in the report on changes in private capital in terms of share capital and share capital, as well as to allocate separate columns in the report for the amount of ordinary shares, preferred shares, stock in reserve and total share capital, share capital (share capital) 020), clearly indicate that the increase in share price (line 030) is due to, cancellation of shares (line 050), decrease in share price (line 060) on a separate line, no need for a separate line for the exchange rate difference, it was proved expedient for the partner companies to deduct the amount of dividends (line 110) from it, indicating “net profit and loss for the reporting period” in a separate line 100 (line 040), with a separate line on contributions and deductions to the charter capital. Line 120 of the report should also include the item “Impact of changes in accounting policies and corrections on errors”. The inclusion of these changes in the report will increase its usefulness.

The content of the report on the cost of goods (works and services), the procedure for its preparation, the essence and methodological aspects of the approach to the preparation of the “statement of profit and loss and other comprehensive income” and the transformation of financial statements on the basis of IFRS.

In the study, financial performance reports showed ways to reduce costs based on advanced methods, including the application of the Variable Costing system in practical examples (Table 7).

Table 8. Profit and Loss Statement in Variable Costing System (thousand soums).

Indicators	2019	2020
Sale, in currency	448,000	536,000
Variable cost of goods sold	188,160	225,120
Production contribution margin	259,840	310,880
Variable sales and administrative costs	80,640	96,480
Contribution margin	179,200	214,400
Constant overhead production costs	98,000	98,000
Fixed sales and administrative costs	52,000	52,000
Total fixed costs	150,000	150,000
Net income	29,200	64,400
Fixed costs relative to sales volume	0,33	0,28

Such an opportunity can only be achieved through the recognition of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) and the preparation of reports in accordance with them. The new version of the Law on Accounting also recognizes that accounting entities may apply IFRSs in the prescribed manner.

The need to apply IFRS is determined by the following factors:

- Investors and shareholders in different countries will have the opportunity to better analyze the financial statements of potential companies based on the same principles, ie comparability;
- It is more appropriate for different stock exchanges in different countries to prepare a single financial statement for each of them, rather than a financial report prepared in accordance with the standards of that country. As a result, reporting costs are reduced and capital raising opportunities are expanded.

International financial reporting refers to financial statements prepared in accordance with IFRS or U.S. GAAP standards. These two types of standards regulate the preparation and submission of financial statements for all stock exchanges around the world and are recognized by these exchanges.

Financial statements prepared based on IFRSs improve the investment climate. It allows large companies to invest in the country.

The current reform of accounting and reporting in our country to international standards is aimed at generating useful information for interested users. Reports prepared using international standards contain a large amount of information about the business entity and ensure the transparency of financial information.

Practice shows that the use of international standards in reporting by an entity allows, firstly, access to international capital markets, and secondly, it can attract investment on more favorable terms. Information about an entity that prepares an IFRS report is sufficient for a potential investor to understand and assess the risks associated with their financing. It should be noted that the main purpose of the conceptual framework is to make IFRS reports as useful as possible for users.[14]

Quality features, fundamental and other features are intended to assist professionals in international standards. However, a separate feature should not be given priority, otherwise the information will not be useful. As O.G. Zhitlukhina points out, "fundamental quality features include a number of other features. For example, the appropriateness of information is affected by the value of the forecast, the importance of the information. Accurate presentation is also influenced by the following features: usefulness of information, objective reflection, absence of errors. Relevance is also included in the fundamental features. The relevance of information means that it can be used for decision-making and evaluation." [8] The full set of financial statements governed by IFRS, First-Time Financial Reporting, includes "balance sheet, profit and loss statement, statement of changes in equity, cash flow statement, accounting policy and explanatory note". All reporting forms are basic and must be compulsorily compiled. It should be noted that the exact name of the listed forms is not mandatory (according to IFRS "First-time application of financial statements") and may be changed by organizations, but at the same time the names of reporting forms should reflect the economic nature of financial indicators should be clear. The first and foremost requirement that an IFRS financial statement must meet is the reliability of the information it reflects.

In our opinion, in order to provide reliable reports to users, it is necessary to:

- ensure compliance with all applicable IFRS;
- Development and consistent application of accounting policies in accordance with IFRS 8 Accounting Policies, Changes and Errors in Accounting Estimates;
- providing information with the following characteristics: comprehensibility, relevance, reliability, and comparability.
- disclosure of additional information, if necessary (especially if compliance with IFRS requirements does not allow to adequately assess the impact of events and operations on the results of operations and financial condition) [9].

It should be noted that a reliable report allows users to predict the future cash flows of the business entity (including the probability and periods of their occurrence), as well as to make effective management decisions based on it. An important aspect in the preparation of reports is the principle of continuity, ie the ability of the business entity to continue its activities on a regular basis.

If there is uncertainty in this matter or the entity plans to cease operations (unless there are other alternative solutions), it is required to disclose these circumstances in the report. Assessing an entity's ability to sustain its operations on a permanent basis, its management must take into account the full range of information about the future for at least 12 months. In our opinion, it is necessary to analyze many factors related to:

- current and future profitability.
- debt repayment terms.
- potential sources of funding, etc.

It is known that business entities are required to submit financial statements under IFRS at least once a year. The report shall reflect the status of the reporting period and the date of completion of the report or its submission for a period shorter or longer than one year, as well as disclose the circumstances of use of such reporting period. Some changes to IFRS require users to be informed in detail about the effect of changes in the estimated values of variables on the activities of the organization on the value of the elements of the financial statements 7 in the future situation [15].

In contrast to IFRS, the order of the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan from December 27, 2002, of No. 140 "About approval of forms of the financial reporting and rules on their filling" a there are no such requirements, but organizations are required to independently determine the content of explanations in reporting forms. IFRS 1, "First-Time Application of Financial Statements," regulates the balance sheet, which does not set strict requirements for its form. Each organization develops a balance sheet form independently. Assets and liabilities are divided into long-term and short-term groups depending on their maturity. If the company deems it inexpedient to be such, assets and liabilities are placed in liquidity order. The list of items to be disclosed in the balance sheet is set out in IFRS 1.

In the balance sheets compiled in our country, in contrast to IFRS, items are strictly divided into long-term and short-term types. It is necessary to develop new standards in the financial reporting of the country, taking into account the views of public organizations to ensure unity with international standards, focusing on the professional opinions of experts in the field of accounting and financial accounting.

Research shows that the main problems in the application of International Financial Reporting Standards in Uzbekistan are: the difficulty of adopting existing and new standards by experts and the lack of information due to the lack of appropriate guidelines and explanations on the application of certain IFRS rules; Lack of a generalized analysis of the practice of applying IFRS in joint stock companies of Uzbekistan; High cost of training in special courses for obtaining international certificates under IFRS; Cost of audit and consulting services provided in accordance with international standards; Lack of IFRS specialists and qualified staff; Automated accounting and reporting software under IFRS, as well as the high cost of their maintenance.

In this regard, the emergence of the official IFRS is an important step towards reforming the country's accounting, making it an effective tool for creating quality, objective, useful and high-demand information. In our opinion, to improve financial reporting, in the context of the application of international standards, it is necessary to:

- simplify some regulatory requirements for the registration of business transactions with primary documents, thereby reducing most of the paperwork.
- giving organizations the right to maintain accounting on the basis of accounting policies developed by them, which fully comply with the requirements of IFRS.
- Establishment of an international high school of accounting to train qualified specialists for the application of IFRS.

Subjects operating in our country can be recommended for foreign experience in preparing the first report on IFRS:

- Pre-planning the preparation of reports on international standards (preparation of schedules and orders for the preparation of the first report, budgeting the salaries of appraisers, auditors, external consultants);
- organization of staff training in accordance with the basic principles of reporting on international standards, considering the specifics of the rules for the first application of IFRS.
- Solve the problem of processing large amounts of accounting data through the use of automated accounting systems, spreadsheets and other programs.[16]

The study found that most scholars divided income into 2 groups, basic operating income and other income. However, other income included non-operating income. The opportunity to include income from non-core activities in itself in other income or to include in operating income is lost. For example, road transport companies are actually engaged in providing one-time services to various events on a contract basis, repairing buses, but this activity is not the main one. Hence, income from such activities is not included in operating income, nor is it included in other income.

The International Financial Reporting Standard also states that income includes income from ordinary activities and other income. In our opinion, here, too, when we say normal activity, we mean basic activity. Let us turn our attention to a brief description of the concept of income and its composition. According to the definition of income and revenue in international standards, income related to the main activity of the enterprise is recognized as income. Other income is expressed in terms of income. In addition, the definition of income from ordinary activities seems to refer to the fact that the enterprise receives income from "unusual activities". That is, the division of income into income and revenue, as well as its content, and its content when divided into types, are somewhat ambiguous. Financial Statements, and the issues related to the accounting of income and expenses.[17]

This Standard defines the concept of profit or loss, according to which profit or loss is the result remaining after deducting expenses from total income, except for other components of gross income. Other aggregate income is the change in equity that occurs as a result of transactions and other events during the period, with the exception of changes in equity transactions with property owners. Other aggregate income includes all parts of 'profit or loss' and 'other aggregate income'. Although the standard uses the terms "other gross income", "profit or loss" and "total gross income", the entity may use other terms to describe the total (final) amounts without losing the meaning. In general, when we study scientific research related to the transition to international standards, using the international standard, we see that researchers have suggested that the terms in the international standard are expressed through direct translation. In some cases, the proposed Uzbek translation of the concepts given in this international standard, or the term used in the international standard itself does not correspond to the stylistics of our own language. This eliminates the possibility of knowing the meaning of the proposed concepts on its behalf, as well as losing the alignment of the sentences. However, as mentioned above, another term can be used in the international standard itself. We will discuss this in more detail in this section states that Financial Statements are a regulated statement of an entity's financial position and financial performance. is composed of. The financial statements also reflect the results of the management of the resources entrusted to it by management.[18]

To achieve this goal, financial statements provide information about the following aspects that are relevant to the business entity: assets; obligations; capital; income and expenses, including profits and losses; contributions made by property owners in their validity as property owners and the amounts distributed to them; cash flows. This information, along with other information in the notes, helps users of the financial statements to predict the entity's future cash flows and, in particular, their timing and accuracy. Depending on the subject of our research and the purpose of our work, we will pay special attention to the revenue and expenditure part. Thus, according to the international standard, financial statements represent information about financial results. Its purpose is also to provide information on financial results. This is somewhat consistent with the report on financial results in our country and its content. In this sentence, the main elements of the financial result are listed one by one, and it is emphasized that the data on income and expenses are the main ones. The fact that information about profits or losses is expressed by the word "inclusive" indicates that it is included in the component of income and expenses. However, most researchers find it necessary to focus on the exact benefits and harms and bring it to the forefront of the report.[19]

According to the standard, the complete set of financial statements includes:

- statement of financial position at the end of the period.
- profit or loss and other comprehensive income statement for the period;
- report on changes in capital for the period;
- cash flow statement for the period;
- comments, ie comments containing a brief description of important accounting policies and other explanatory information;

- comparative information for the previous period, etc. As a continuation of the above content, the name of the report is left to the discretion of the entity, specifies that the entity may use other names than the reporting names used in the standard. There is a requirement in the financial statements to present the financial results fairly, in accordance with the definitions and recognition criteria for income and expenses. In accordance with the requirements of International Financial Reporting Standards, information representing financial results should include items in the profit or loss section or profit or loss statement for the period that appear in the following amounts: income from operating activities; gains and losses arising from the derecognition of financial assets at amortized cost; financial expenses; the share of profit and loss of dependent business entities and joint ventures accounted for by the share accounting method; any gain or loss arising from the difference between the carrying amount of the asset and its fair value at the date of its reclassification when the financial asset is reclassified and carried at fair value; a single amount for total liquidated activities. In accordance with the requirements of International Financial Reporting Standards, if the information contained in the income statement or other consolidated income statement or notes is significant items of income or expense, the business entity must disclose their nature and amount separately [20].

Circumstances in which items of income and expense may need to be disclosed include: reducing the carrying amount of inventories to their net realizable value or the carrying amount of property, plant and equipment to their recoverable amount and restoring such reductions; restructuring of the business entity and the restoration of any reserves made at the expense of restructuring; write-off of fixed assets; write-off of investments; non-ongoing activities; court proceedings; and the recovery of formed reserves in other cases. An entity shall present the costs recognized in profit or loss using a classification based on their nature or function in the entity, whichever provides more reliable and relevant information. Expenses are classified into secondary categories that can be differentiated according to their frequency of recurrence, potential for profit or loss, and their predictability, to highlight the components of financial results.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The purpose of financial accounting and reporting, the subjects of accounting, the subject (object), rules and principles, method (methods and techniques), procedure and cycle, the product of the accounting process, the availability of information users are the factors determining its formation as an independent science. Improved definitions of the concept of “financial reporting” by defining the information contained in the financial statements and clarifying the sequence of implementation and the process of reorganization, as well as the characteristics of financial reporting, classification by different features of financial reporting, the systematization of a group of information users plays an important role in improving the theoretical foundations of financial reporting. The inclusion of key principles such as consistency, objectivity and fairness in the fundamental quality characterization principles recognized by the international community harmonizes conceptual rules with international standards, strengthens the regulatory framework of accounting and ensures the transparency of financial statements.

Improving the content and structure of the “Cash Flow Statement” in accordance with international and national standards and the requirements of the transformation will allow to prepare the report directly and indirectly on the basis of the statement of financial position and the statement of profit and loss and other comprehensive income. The development of transformation formulas as a methodological solution to these problems facilitates the compilation of the report, ensuring the accuracy and interdependence of its data.

The “Report on changes in private capital” includes the allocation of authorized capital to share capital and share capital, as well as the full formation of share capital and separate columns for ordinary shares (nominal value), preferred shares, reserve shares and total share capital and their movements the development of proposals for the separation of leading lines will bring the report in line with international standards and increase its ability to carry useful information. The proposed new format of this report ensures the interconnectedness of the reporting forms and the transformation based on international financial reporting standards.

National Accounting Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 8 “Consolidated Financial Statements and Accounting for Investments in Subsidiaries”, registered on December 28, 1998, No. 580 for the application of a single international accounting policy for consolidated financial statements, taking into account the characteristics of companies The introduction of specific aspects of insurance activities within the requirements of IFRS, financial consolidation and the development of specific financial analysis indicators on the basis of normative documents.

1) Ensuring the uniformity of accounting data for various insurance companies in the insurance market within the requirements of international practice and a single system of criteria for its analysis before the formation of consolidated financial statements of insurance companies in Uzbekistan.

2) When compiling the consolidated financial statements of insurance companies, it is necessary to remove the balances in the turnover and accounts of reinsurance transactions between the participants of the economic association and make adjustments to the relevant accounting accounts.

3) It is necessary to develop uniform regulations and guidelines for ensuring the comparability of consolidated financial statements of insurance companies and reporting data in accordance with IFRS 17) "Insurance contracts" of participants in the economic merger of insurance companies.

4) Lack of a single methodological framework for the formation of consolidated financial statements of insurance companies therefore, methodological recommendations on identification and identification of intra-group transactions in order to eliminate them, and the implementation of the above sequence and consolidation steps, are necessary.

In summary, the consolidation procedure is achieved by ensuring the integrity of IFRS accounts, accounting policies and worksheets used in the group of insurance companies, keeping records in accordance with IFRS and selecting the most appropriate method of preparing financial statements.

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